

Imaging-PHD: Empowering data reuse and reproducibility through microscopy-community-defined Persistent Hardware Descriptors

Lay Summary: Capturing the precise hardware configuration of an instrument that has generated scientific data is critical to understanding, reproducing and sharing the results. Though registries exist to provide unique identifiers for instrument models (e.g., RRID) and individual instruments themselves (e.g., PIDINST), no current method exists to capture the hardware configuration of an instrument with sufficient detail to promote data quality, reproducibility and FAIR sharing. This proposal introduces Persistent Hardware Descriptors (PHDs), specifically in light-microscopy, to solve the problem of inadequate metadata capture and storage, which hinders research reproducibility, data integrity, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. By providing a standardized framework for capturing this essential information, the project enhances the reliability of scientific results, makes advanced technologies more accessible, and supports long-term data preservation, ultimately advancing scientific research practices. Specifically, Imaging-PHD will (1) establish a vendor-friendly framework for describing hardware configurations that can be used in publications associated with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), (2) create a collaborative space where configurations can be reviewed and edited before being published, including a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) for authoring microscopy configurations when vendor software does not create them automatically, and (3) launch a coordinated outreach effort to educate vendors and users, provide training for utilizing the resulting tools effectively, and generate a corpus of hardware descriptions to drive improvements in quality control and enable community-wide LLM approaches through high quality training data. All components of this proposal are designed to be interoperable and expandable for implementation at other multiple sites and within various scientific disciplines.

Short Lay Summary: This proposal introduces Persistent Hardware Descriptors (PHDs) for microscopy to improve metadata capture and storage for scientific research. The objectives include establishing a standardized framework for documenting hardware configurations, creating a collaborative space for editing and publishing these configurations, and launching an outreach program to educate and train users on using these tools. This project aims to enhance research reproducibility, data integrity, and cross-disciplinary collaboration with a design that is interoperable across various research domains.

B. PROJECT SUMMARY

Persistent Hardware Descriptors (PHDs) provide fault-tolerant, distributed, low-cost cyberinfrastructure (CI) for the citable description of the complex and changing configurations of instrument hardware captured during every data acquisition session, thus enhancing rigor, reproducibility, data reuse, and the recognition of technical staff, while democratizing access to advanced technologies and scientific information. This project addresses the critical need for improved data management through enhanced metadata capture and storage with possible applications to fundamental biology, physics, material, geological, earth, and environmental sciences and engineering.

Overview:

To demonstrate the feasibility of PHD, **the Imaging-PHD project concentrates on light-microscopy** and provides: (1) a **vendor-friendly framework** named Next-Generation Metadata (NGM) for automatically transferring hardware metadata from instrument manufacturers to researchers; (2) a **user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI)** named Micro-Meta Platform Frontend for authoring, reviewing and editing NGM-encoded Hardware Descriptors; (3) a **service infrastructure** named Micro-Meta Platform Backend for interlinking client applications with permanent identifier creation and repository deposition. MMPB will include exploratory LLM approaches for metadata extraction from instrument technical descriptions. (4) **Outreach efforts** to disseminate the project's results, educating the research community from multiple domains on the added value of linking hardware metadata with the persistent identification of instruments, samples, and data and training users to best utilize the generated CI. **As added value, this effort will generate a corpus of hardware descriptors to drive improvements in quality control and enable community-wide LLM approaches.** The flagship installation will be hosted at UMass Chan Med and provide persistent storage for Hardware Descriptors, an Elasticsearch-enabled dashboard, and smart visualization. Future installations will join a federated network, creating PHDs in microscopy and beyond. **Keywords:** CloudAccess, Community, Cross-disciplinary, Data reuse, Distributed, Equitable, FAIR, Hardware configurations, Machine-actionable, Microscopy Metadata, Persistent identifiers, Citable.

Intellectual Merits:

The capture and reporting of machine-actionable metadata are essential for researchers across multiple disciplines to generate high-quality, reproducible, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) scientific data. This goal is furthered by documenting the full life-cycle (provenance) of data. This project contributes to producing and managing scientific outputs by expanding the current publishing infrastructure to enable **persistent linking of samples, reagents, and data to rich, detailed, and citable hardware descriptors of individual instruments.** The automation of these descriptions will eliminate tedious manual data entry, in turn improving reliability and efficiency. As a proof of principle, the project focuses on implementing these concepts in bioimaging. Nevertheless, all outputs will be developed to be extensible to and interoperable with other domains and fields of research.

Broader Impacts:

The PHD project's broader impact centers on empowering **researchers to produce data that can be harmonized, interpreted, pooled, and reanalyzed across different origins, thus expediting further scientific progress.** To this aim, Imaging-PHD leverages community work carried out by the team in the context of BioImaging North America, Quality Assessment, and REProducibility for Instruments and Images in Light Microscopy, the Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities, and the Open Microscopy Environment. By enabling public and citable descriptions of instrument instances used to produce individual datasets, Imaging-PHD will **allow researchers to accurately report data generation methods** in scientific publications and data repositories, thus fostering scientific validity and reliability. Imaging-PHD will **continue to collaborate with global instrumentation manufacturers** to improve technical standards and meet the changing needs of the research community and industry. At the same time, by sharing standardized information about research instrumentation, Imaging-PHD will **improve the sustainability of the research ecosystem**, ensure quality, and **democratize access** to scientific information and often prohibitively expensive research resources. Finally, the project will significantly impact scientists' awareness of and **access to research data management and sharing** for rigor and data reuse.

D. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

D1. Intellectual Merits

The advancement of science demands efficient re-utilization of high-quality FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)¹ data, which in turn is dependent on a deep understanding and trust of the methods that produced it. Since 2018, the global imaging community has built substantial traction towards unified reporting guidelines, metadata specifications and calibration protocols²⁻⁷. This is reflected in special journal issues on these topics and work by new community organizations like QUAREP^{6,8-10} (for abbreviations see Textbox 1). For many bioimaging organizations, transnational consortia, and scientific instrumentation companies, however, there is a common roadblock towards achieving standards and norms. The use of persistent and extensible rich metadata across these

Textbox 1 – Glossary		
Full name	Abbrev.	Description
4D Nucleome	4DN	An NIH-funded initiative to understand nuclear organization.
Association of Biomeolecular Resource Facilities	ABRF	The premier association of North American core facilities managers and personnel.
BioImaging North America	BINA	A community initiative of more than 800 bioimaging scientists across North America.
CoreMarketplace		The ABRF-sponsored persistent registry of life-sciences core facilities listing available resources.
Digital Research Alliance of Canada	DRAC	A Canada government-funded initiative to promote the broad adoption of FAIR RDMS and research computing practices.
4DN-BINA-OME Microscopy Metadata	NBO	An expansion of the OME Data Model that was published by 4DN and BINA to capture Microscopy Metadata.
NBO-QUAREP Microscopy Metadata	NBO-Q	A consensus revision of NBO that is being developed by QUAREP-LiMi in collaboration with microscope manufacturers.
Microscopy Metadata	MM	Required to ensure image data quality, reproducibility and reuse (i.e., Hardware Specifications, Acquisitions Settings and QC metadata).
Micro-Meta App	MMA	An existing Javascript downloadable application for authoring Hardware Descriptors based on the NBO specifications.
Micro-Meta Explorer	MME	An existing Javascript React component for finding and comparing existing Hardware Descriptors.
Open Microscopy Environment	OME	A consortium of universities, research labs, industry and developers producing open-source software and format standards for microscopy data.
Quality Assessment and Reproducibility for Light Microscopy	QUAREP	A global initiative of more than 550 light microscopists from academia and industry working to develop consensus quality control procedures and microscopy metadata standards.
Research Data Alliance	RDA	A forum for > 1000 global members to develop and adopt infrastructure for data-sharing and data-driven research.
Persistent Hardware Descriptors	PHD	Project to enable the persistent identification of instrument Hardware Descriptors and their linking to instrument instances.
Next-Generation Metadata	NGM	A composable metadata framework (Obj. 1, Fig. 4) to define, capture and exchange of community-specified microscope Hardware Descriptors.
Micro-Meta Platform Backend	MMPB	The Micro-Meta Platform Backend (Obj. 3, Fig. 5, 6 and 7).
Micro-Meta Platform Frontend	MMPF	The Micro-Meta App and Explorer based frontend of Micro-Meta Platform (Obj. 2, Fig 5. and 6).
Research Resources	RRID	Used here to identify Core Facilities and instrument models.
Persistent Identification of Instruments	PIDINST	Used here to persistently identify research-grade instrument instances and to interlink with PHD and RRID-identified Cores.
PHD Identifier	PHD-ID	The persistent identifier utilized for Persistent Hardware Descriptors.

communities is needed to **link samples, instrumentation, resulting data, publications and Research Data Management and Sharing (RDMS) platform in an open way that maximizes research integrity, data reuse and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Persistent Hardware Descriptors (PHD) provide this cyberinfrastructure (CI) enabling a persistent record of detailed instrument Hardware Descriptors within the publication ecosystem while expediting their discovery and re-use.**

Project Motivation and Impact

Science-driven

Scientific instruments play a pivotal role in research across diverse disciplines, spanning the life-sciences, physics, geology, chemistry and engineering. Accurate identification and description of individual instruments, enabled by globally unique Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and metadata registries, are crucial for documenting experimental methods and linking instruments with samples, resulting data (i.e., data provenance)¹¹⁻¹³, the scientific literature, RDMS platform, and the institutions, core facilities and individuals involved in research¹⁴⁻¹⁸ (Fig.1). Tracking each unique device, rather than solely recording its model (i.e., class), avoids tedious data entry, streamlines institutional inventories for strategic planning, reporting and funding purposes, promotes access to scientific information and advanced technologies, enhances the sustainability of core facilities through the recognition of their essential role in scientific advancement and optimizes resource utilization^{14,16,19,20}. As such, **instrument PIDs are essential for reproducibility, data trust and sharing²¹, credit attribution to core facilities, the equitable and efficient use of research resources and ensuring adherence to FAIR data principles^{1,14,16,17,20,22}.**

Two projects provide key building blocks for the persistent identification and description of instruments. The RRID²³⁻²⁵-enabled CoreMarketplace^{26,68} (developed by AB & NH, governed by sample authorities such as the AntibodyRegistry.org and Cellosaurus.org; endorsed by ABRF, ARRIVE²⁷, MDAR²⁸, and NISO JATS²⁹; adopted by unfund. collab. YCharOS³⁰ and OGA³¹) is the **platform of choice to uniquely identify core facilities³² and instrument classes** (i.e., Models). This platform dovetails with the well-established RRIDs used by labs and core facilities to track metadata for reagents and samples such

as antibodies, plasmids, cell lines, and organisms^{25,33,34} and link them to related data (e.g., validation data)^{30,31,35-37} and publications. PIDINST (developed by unfund. collab. Stocker)^{22,38} provides a **robust metadata schema**³⁹ for the **global identification of instrument instances**, information retrieval, and workflow integration³⁹. It has been endorsed by RDA^{22,40} and DRAC⁴¹⁻⁴³, can be implemented^{44,45} as DOI⁴⁶ via DataCite⁴⁷, and was adopted for a wide variety of instrument types by NIST⁴⁸, EUDAT B2INST⁴⁹, and others⁵⁰. Despite these advances, it is not possible to capture the detailed technical description of the hardware configuration of complex and evolving instruments at the time of data generation. PHD addresses this gap by leveraging robust technologies like RRID/CoreMarketplace and PIDINST, which were selected as they are the most widely adopted solutions for building PID frameworks for instrument Models and instances. The ultimate goal is to create a comprehensive provenance chain, persistently linking data to samples, instruments, analysis procedures, publications and RDMS systems.

Textbox 2 – Imaging-PHD Use Cases

Instrument Manufacturers Community Partnership: The over 650-member strong QUAREP-LiMi consortium is actively collaborating with nine leading global microscopy camera manufacturers (Andor, Evident Olympus, Hamamatsu, Leica, Nikon, PCO, Roper Teledyne, Scientifica, Zeiss) to provide community-defined technical descriptions of cameras. This will be followed by similar work on other microscope components, aiming to enhance image data quality and reproducibility. The Imaging-PHD framework will allow manufacturers to supply researchers with community-specified Hardware Descriptor files for instruments according to these technical specifications. This approach will facilitate transparency in instrument purchasing and ensure ongoing instrument performance monitoring after delivery.

Industry partners: Microscope instrumentation vendors often need to monitor the usage patterns and performance of specific instrument models and their individual units to better understand their customers. The Imaging-PHD CI is ideally suited for these industry partners, as it allows for effective tracking of individual instrument instances as they are deployed in the field.

Research Labs: Graduate students and undergrads may want to conduct complex imaging experiments that require microscope instruments not available to them. The Imaging-PHD extension of the CoreMarketplace capabilities would be transformative by enabling students to identify and access the appropriate microscope at a nearby core facility.

Core Facilities: Facility managers often aim to increase revenue and demonstrate the broader impact of their microscopy core by attracting more users from within and outside their institutions. The powerful search engine to be included in the Imaging-PHD platform will transform customers' ability to find the instruments they need based on standardized technical descriptions, thereby increasing facility usage.

We seek funding to develop **Imaging-PHD** (Fig.2), focusing on light-microscopy where **the potential scientific impact is massive for imaging scientists**⁵¹ **across different expertise levels, disciplines, geographical areas, and socioeconomic backgrounds**, (see Sect. H of “Equipment, Facilities and Other Resources” - EFOR). Modern-day light-microscopy is a sophisticated, quantitative and rapidly evolving technology integral to multiple disciplines, including material sciences, nanotechnology and semiconductor engineering. In the life-sciences, microscopes are found at nearly every experimental laboratory across industry, academia and educational institutions as well as in one of the thousands of core facilities worldwide, where expert staff ensure the maintenance and utilization of advanced microscopes. This widespread distribution explains why images are included in 500 newly published articles/day, in the life-sciences alone^{52,53}, and the expanding global microscope market size was estimated at USD 7-11 billion^{54,55}.

Despite the prevalence and potential impact of microscopes, the production of FAIR image data remains challenging. Researchers often lack sufficient expertise in microscopy⁵⁶ and data management to produce reliable and quantitative image data, leading to difficulties in interpreting acquired data, reproducing experiments, and sharing results⁵⁷⁻⁶¹. Experiments using microscopes vary in complexity and objectives, leading to different reporting and Quality Control (QC) requirements¹². Additionally, metadata automatically recorded by microscopes from different manufacturers varies widely. This often leads to poor characterization of microscope configuration and performance during imaging. However, accurately tracking data provenance from acquisition through analysis and visualization is vital to ensure scientific rigor and maximizes the impact of image data.^{2,3,5,11,12,62,63} Although microscopes have a finite number of hardware components, the complexity arising from their combination grows quickly (e.g., EFOR, Fig.2)^{8,64,65}. There are currently no universally adopted frameworks ensuring the capture of this complex space covering Hardware Specifications, Acquisitions Settings and Performance Metrics (collectively termed **Microscopy Metadata - MM**)^{2,12}. The implementation and universal adoption of metadata frameworks and automated data management pipelines incorporating PIDs is essential for bridging the gap between sophisticated technology and researchers' expertise, thus expediting multidisciplinary scientific discovery.

Innovation

To address these fundamental scientific challenges, Dr. Caterina Strambio-De-Castilla (CSDC) will lead the Imaging-PHD project, which involves recognized scientists in microscopy and RDMS (see Team composition and abbreviations in MCP), to deliver **CI that can capture, search, and display complex but machine-actionable Hardware Descriptors of scientific instruments** (Figs. 1-2) by leveraging existing key components of the data management ecosystem (PIDs, repositories). All senior members of the team play integral roles in global community initiatives that are spearheading the generation, stewardship and sharing of FAIR data. Such initiatives include **4DN**^{66,67}, **ABRF**⁶⁸, **BINA**⁶⁹, **Canada BioImaging (CBI)**⁷⁰, **DRAC**⁴¹, **German BioImaging (GerBi)**⁷¹, **Global BioImaging (GBI)**^{72,73}, **OME**⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶, the **RRID-powered CoreMarketplace**, **PIDINST**^{22,38,39}, and **QUAREP**^{6,77} (see Sect. H, EFOR). Because of this multidisciplinary involvement, the Imaging-PHD platform will be far-reaching across disciplines to promote data quality, reproducibility, and reuse as well as the efficient and equitable access to scientific information and research resources and the sustainability of the research enterprise. To maximize impact, Imaging-PHD was designed to address user-needs that were collected by team members through personal and community interactions (Textbox 2). The new platform will solve key issues within the light-microscopy domain while also laying the groundwork for a persistent mechanism to augment the current publication paradigm. PHD extends the existing network of public repositories (Figs.5&7) with semantically rich documents that can be queried and referenced. This innovative approach builds on the existing sustainability of libraries and repositories so that all PIDs will continue to resolve, independently of dedicated PHD funding, while enabling enhanced functionality like search and exploration as long as the scientific CI is maintained.

D.2 Work Plan Outline

Imaging-PHD simplifies the generation and publication of high-quality and FAIR microscopy datasets by enabling persistently-identified Hardware Descriptors captured using the Micro-Meta Platform to meet the community-defined **4DN-BINA-OME-QUAREP (NBO-Q)² MM** specifications (led by CSDC and DG)¹². The connection with the OME project (led by JM) ensures instrument metadata is closely tied to acquired data, facilitating the smooth transfer of information from instrument manufacturers to microscope custodians and users. Leveraging the community CoreMarketplace/RRID infrastructure to persistently identify core facilities and instrument classes), **PIDINST**³⁸ for instrument instances and the UMass Chan Library DataCite license for assigning DOIs, Imaging-PHD will furnish resolvable PIDs for instrument models, instances (individually configured microscopes in specific, unique locations) and Hardware Descriptors to ensure the inter-linking with institutional inventories, core facilities, microscopes, image data, reporting documents and scientific publications (Fig.1). The Imaging-PHD objectives (Fig.3) are: **(1) Next-Generation Metadata (NGM)**: This composable metadata framework (Fig.4) enables the definition, capture and exchange of community-specified Hardware Descriptors. Based on the Resource Description Framework (RDF), NGM documents form an interlinked graph of metadata covering all states of acquisition systems. Designed for extension by instrument manufacturers, NGM can be user-authored or generated during acquisition, e.g., by embedding in the emerging bioimaging standard, Next-Generation

Fig. 1: Persistent Hardware Descriptors (PHD) extend the capabilities of Research Resource Identifiers (RRID and Persistent Identifier for Instruments (PIDINST) by providing detailed configuration information. Permanently recording the configuration of unique devices rather than solely recording model information empowers both research scientists (blue) and core facilities personnel (orange) by promoting the association of instruments with: (A) the data they produce for tracking data provenance; (B) image data repositories for interoperability and FAIR data sharing; (C) performance metrics for QC; (D) scientific literature for the citations of research resources; (E) experimental protocols for reproducibility; (F) institutional inventories, funding proposals and financial reports for increasing their efficiency, accuracy and utility; (G) institutional and core facilities websites and inventories to promote the: (i) efficient selection and equitable access to resources (Brown *et al.*, 2022; Meyn *et al.*, 2022); (ii) financial sustainability and recognition of core facilities; and (iii) workforce educational and training.

File Formats (NGFF)^{78,79}. **(2) User-friendly Micro-Meta Platform Frontend (MMPF):** A front-end Graphical User Interface (GUI) based on the existing **Micro-Meta App (MMA)**^{80,81} and **Micro-Meta Explorer (MME)**⁸² will be used for authoring microscope Hardware Descriptors^{2,12}, finding microscopes with specific characteristics and comparing them across institutional and regional laboratories and facilities. **(3) Re-usable Micro-Meta Platform Backend (MMPB):** Service components (Fig.5) running at UMass Chan will provide pre-publication management of Hardware Descriptors associated with individual instruments and facilitate their citable publication (Fig.6) by supporting: (i) **Persistently identifying** instrument models and instances through integration with CoreMarketplace/RRID and PIDINST; (ii) linking persistently identified instruments with RRID-identified core facilities; (iii) **minting PHD-Identifiers (PHD-IDs)** implemented as DOIs for individual Hardware Descriptors through the institutional UMass Chan Library DataCite license; (iv) **exploring LLM-efforts** to automatically extract NBO-Q² compliant metadata from instrument technical description files. MMPB will also leverage the Elasticsearch-based Foundry ETL-system^{83,84} for discovering published Hardware Descriptors online and aggregating them for search and exploration (Fig.7). **(4) Coordinated Testing, Validation, Outreach and Dissemination (CTVOD):** A coordinated strategy to promote adoption, training and education will be key to the broader impact of Imaging-PHD. This will include: (i) directly involving research scientists, core-facility personnel and data librarians during development to ensure the usability of produced software tools; (ii) enacting a targeted plan of action to educate users about the importance of FAIR practices, including the use of PIDs and metadata registries for the success of the research enterprise, and provide training for the effective utilization of the resulting CI; (iii) creating a collection of technical descriptions for microscopy-related hardware to facilitate future LLM-based community-learning.

Fig. 2: PHDs provide a record of hardware changes over time: Beyond the out-of-the-box model and basic metadata information provided by RRID and PIDINST, respectively, each PHD faithfully records the configuration of an instrument, at a given time. For example, PHD-ID:0000 is the initial configuration on setup. PHD-ID:0001 records the replacement of the light-source, while PHD-ID:0002 additionally records a new stage.

UMass Chan Library DataCite license; (iv) **exploring LLM-efforts** to automatically extract NBO-Q² compliant metadata from instrument technical description files. MMPB will also leverage the Elasticsearch-based Foundry ETL-system^{83,84} for discovering published Hardware Descriptors online and aggregating them for search and exploration (Fig.7). **(4) Coordinated Testing, Validation, Outreach and Dissemination (CTVOD):** A coordinated strategy to promote adoption, training and education will be key to the broader impact of Imaging-PHD. This will include: (i) directly involving research scientists, core-facility personnel and data librarians during development to ensure the usability of produced software tools; (ii) enacting a targeted plan of action to educate users about the importance of FAIR practices, including the use of PIDs and metadata registries for the success of the research enterprise, and provide training for the effective utilization of the resulting CI; (iii) creating a collection of technical descriptions for microscopy-related hardware to facilitate future LLM-based community-learning.

The Imaging-PHD project will demonstrate how vexing gaps in the current research data landscape can be bridged by offering a comprehensive CI solution for the persistent identification and tracking of Hardware Descriptors in microscopy. By providing reusable components for researchers, core facilities, and vendors to consistently document and share detailed descriptions of any hardware configuration, the PHD project drastically improves data quality and reuse, enhances collaboration, promotes the recognition of the key role of scientists and core facilities in the research enterprise, and promote a more efficient use of resources. Furthermore, Imaging-PHD is designed to mitigate interoperability risks across diverse instruments, modalities, and disciplines: (1) The rapid pace of advancements in light microscopy (e.g., spatial omics, AI-based acquisition modalities, etc.) makes it essential to develop solutions that are inherently extensible and adaptable. (2) The choice of interoperable solutions such as CoreMarketplace/RRID and PIDINST, ensures that Imaging-PHD will be widely applicable. (3) W3C standards, modular architecture, and Representational State Transfer (REST) API protocols will enhance extensibility. (4) Collaboration with imaging, PID, and RDMS initiatives (see EFOR, Sect. H) will promote consensus, adoption and interoperability across communities. In short, this proposal will contribute to the development of a cohesive and standardized approach to managing complex data, ultimately improving the overall quality and impact of research as a whole.

D.3 Background

The Need for FAIR Data Principles in the Life Sciences

To be broadly and equitably impactful, advances in the life sciences depend on the generation of FAIR^{1,85} datasets that can be reused in a democratized manner. Funding agencies and publishers increasingly

emphasize RDMS throughout the research lifecycle. Given the growing volume and complexity of data, computational support is essential for the progress of biological research. FAIR principles facilitate automated data discovery, support reuse by other scientists across diverse backgrounds, geographical areas and financial statuses, facilitate knowledge discovery, and enhance research quality. They are imperative as data interpretation hinges on a thorough understanding of its provenance (from the sample to acquisition to quantitative result extraction)^{11,12,6263,86} and quality (including instrument performance)^{6,77}. Implementing "FAIRness" (including PIDs, standardized metadata schemas and interoperable RDMS systems) is a necessity to catalyze scientific discovery and ensures the highest research quality.

Impact of Persistent Identification of research entities

The use of PIDs^{22,25,46,87-90} is widely recognized to be key for research integrity^{42,48,91} and have demonstrated financial and efficiency benefits^{14,16}. In addition, PIDs have been shown to more broadly impact equity in research resource allocation, sustainability, automation, and strategic decision making, ultimately enhancing the open use of science (see LoC from unfund. collab. Lariviers, UNESCO Chair for Open Science). However, identifiers alone do not sufficiently capture all necessary information needed to reconstruct scientific experiments, especially in microscopy.

Addressing challenges in microscopy data management

For reliable and reproducible extraction of quantitative information, microscopes must be well-described using community-accepted metadata specifications^{2,5,12,76,80,92,93}. Challenges in producing high-quality FAIR image data include the limited enforcement of existing guidelines by vendors, researchers, funders, and scientific publishers and the rapid pace of imaging technical development regularly introduces new metadata needs. Tackling these challenges with CI such as the proposed Imaging-PHD is critical for ensuring that the full potential of microscopy data is realized in the life sciences and beyond.

Community Initiatives Promoting Microscopy Quality, Reproducibility and Data Reuse

Community initiatives like QUAREP^{6,77} bring together imaging scientists to promote consensus on best practices for quality, reproducibility, and data reuse in light microscopy. Involving key stakeholders (instrument manufacturers, journal editors, and professional associations)^{69,94-99}, these initiatives advance FAIR practices through shared QC best-practices, metadata standards, and community outreach. As proof-of-principle, CSDC and DG are leading an effort with nine global vendors (Andor, Hamamatsu, Roper Telydyne, Scientifica, and unfund. collabs. Evident Olympus, Leica, Nikon, PCO, Zeiss) to produce consensus camera metadata specifications based on NBO-Q² and quality criteria (Textbox 2). These initiatives foster standardization of Hardware Descriptors and improve microscopy data quality and reuse.

D.4 Preliminary Data

Results from prior NSF support: NSF 1917206 to DG. Work products are teaching materials for microscopy courses including 3D printed microscopes for classroom assembly, asynchronous online learning modules, 3D microscope assembly game (online, assessment tool) and contributions to multiple publications^{2,3,80}. This grant supported one post doc, two PhD students and six REU/RAHSS students in the lab. The REU/RAHSS program developed here will be further supported as part of this CSSI application.

D.5 Cyberinfrastructure plan

Building on existing, recognized capabilities

DICOM, OME and the Status of image data and metadata standards in light microscopy

Obj.	Deliverable	Yr. 1-1	Yr. 1-2	Yr. 2-1	Yr. 2-2	Yr. 3-1	Yr. 3-2	Yr. 4-1	Yr. 4-2
1 - Definition of NGM	1-1 Core Linked Data Framework								
	1-2 Hardware Descriptor Schema								
	1-3 Software Components								
	1-4 Storage Backends								
	1-5 Community/Vendor Coordination								
2 - Devel. of MMPE	2-1 Extend Base Client Capabilities			Development			Supp.		
	2-2 Reading and Writing NGM				Development		Support		
	2-3 Integration with the Micro-Meta Platform Backend					Development			
3 - Development of MMPB	3-1 Micro-Meta Platform Development & Deployment		Development						
	3-2 Micro-Meta Platform Maintenance/Support						Support		
	3-3 Synchronization of RRID with CoreMarketplace		Development				Support		
	3-4 Automate the Seamless Generation of PIDs						Development		
	3-5 PHD-aware Search Indexing Enhancements		Devel.				Support		
4 - CTVOD	4-1 Consulting ahead of development								
	4-2 Improved usability by integrated user-evaluation								
	4-3 Training and Education Strategy								
	4.4 Curated corpus of microscope technical material								

Fig. 3: PHD Objectives Gantt Chart. When relevant a distinction is made between phases of active development versus support.

Whereas standards for RDMS have been introduced for some biological research methods, such as genomics or cytometry¹⁰⁰⁻¹⁰⁴, a complete solution for optical microscopy in the life sciences does not yet exist. Though DICOM¹⁰⁵ has succeeded in the development of standard image data formats and workflows for medical imaging technologies, this has not resulted in wide adoption in the fundamental life sciences, despite the recent addition to data repositories¹⁰⁶ in support of some microscopy modalities^{107,108} like whole slide imaging^{109,110}. A more complete covering of life science modalities is provided by OME which has worked since 2000 to establish the *de facto* standard for meeting the combined needs of industry and academia. Led by team member JM and unfund. collab. J. Swedlow, OME develops the OME Data Model^{74,75}, the OME-TIFF file format¹¹¹, the Bio-Formats conversion library¹¹², the OMERO repository⁷⁶ and more recently, a NGFF^{78,79} initiative to create a bioimaging file format standard¹¹³ (OME-Zarr⁷⁹). Together these tools enable the open exchange, FAIR RDMS, and processing of data obtained from a wide range of microscopy modalities and technologies and stored in over 160 formats today. However, to fully capture the hardware metadata produced by thousands of daily users thus truly enabling a standard file format, the OME framework requires an extensible metadata framework, such as NGM, to capture a wide array of instrument types and data modalities across different scientific disciplines possibly even serving as a bridge for future harmonization with DICOM.

4DN-BINA-OME Microscopy Metadata Specifications and REMBI guidelines

As a first example of building community specifications for capturing hardware metadata for the ever increasing variety of light microscopy technologies, the 4DN^{66,67,114} Imaging WG, under the leadership of CSDC and DG, launched a collaboration with BINA¹¹⁵ to expand the OME Data Model^{74,75} to ensure the quality, reproducibility and reuse of FISH omics experiments^{12,116}. This resulted in the publication of the NBO MM specifications^{2,117}, which are modular, tiered, and designed to support multiple modalities^{2,12}. NBO has since been adopted by the QUAREP global initiative^{6,77,118} leading to the NBO-QUAREP (NBO-Q)² revision in partnership with microscope hardware manufacturers^{119,120} (Textbox 2). As such, NBO-Q fulfills one of the 8 metadata categories defined in **Recommended Metadata For Biological Images (REMBI)**⁵. Co-authored by 46 community members including CSDC, DG, and JM, these recommendations cover a broad range of imaging modalities, describe all imaging datasets deposited to BioImage Archive¹²¹, and form the basis for further multi-disciplinary harmonization through the JM-led foundingGIDE initiative¹²². NBO-Q builds on REMBI demonstrating the need and feasibility of NGM and MMPF⁸⁰.

Micro-Meta App and Explorer

While the establishment of data formats and metadata standards are important, software tools that expedite the capture, visualization and exploration of MM^{2,12} are essential to maximize scientific impact. MMA^{80,81} provides a user-friendly GUI and implements NBO-Q² to capture and organize hardware specification and image acquisition settings for image datasets produced using light microscopes. It provides an ideal platform for training users on the intricacies of hardware configurations and was adopted by 4DN^{66,67,114,123} and HuBMAP¹²⁴⁻¹²⁶, whose research coordination center is led by unfund. collab P. Blood (see EFOR, Sect. H). The MME⁸² provides complementary query and comparison functionalities to identify appropriate microscopes and evaluate their capabilities. As Javascript React components, both MMA and MME can be integrated in third-party frameworks, e.g. the 4DN-Data Portal^{114,123}. As such, MMA and MME are ideally suited to serve as a frontend for the proposed Micro-Meta Platform.

ABRF CoreMarketplace

The Vermont Biomedical Research Network¹²⁷ created CoreMarketplace²⁶ in partnership with ABRF as a central registry to assign RRIDs²³⁻²⁵ to research core facilities across various institutions and scientific disciplines. This promotes the discoverability of facilities and instruments, attracts potential customers, encourages collaboration, expedites usage monitoring, and enhances the recognition of research activities needed for sustainability and funding. Furthermore, by leveraging the USED.it database¹²⁸, CoreMarketplace extends the use of RRIDs to instrument Models (i.e., classes), thus facilitating the tracking of data quality & provenance and scientific citation. Because of its ability to link with the full imaging data provenance chain and inherent interoperability CoreMarketplace/RRID provides an ideal foundation for the Imaging-PHD project.

Foundry Technology and Elasticsearch engine

The FAIR Data Informatics Lab at UCSD has created the Foundry, an open source set of cloud-native applications and services based on the Elasticsearch technology that was developed for DataMed.org⁸³. The Foundry is a simple, federated system on which the Imaging-PHD project will be based. It uses open REST interfaces and a common schema for interoperability with other RDMS systems. The Foundry is currently used by several other projects showing scalability and robustness, including: the federated RRID system (~30 databases aggregated and constantly updated), dkNet.org (a data search platform for digestive and kidney disorder researchers), and the Neuroscience Information Framework (a data search platform for neuroscience researchers). The Elasticsearch-based Foundry technology will be used to stand up a federated search system that will serve the needs of the proposed CI.

Enterprise cloud-based solutions for research data at UMass Chan

UMass Chan's cloud infrastructure, hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS; for more details, see EFOR, Sect. E.1.3 and “Cloud Computing Resources” - CCR), is managed by professional staff to comply with federal and international regulations, including SOC1 Type II, SOC2 Type II, and ISO 27001. Tailored for enhanced security, the platform includes single sign-on, secure public interfaces, scalable high-availability resources, and fine-grained access controls via AWS Identity and Access Management (IAM). AWS's multi-region redundancy safeguards against data loss and disruption, while comprehensive policies ensure resource efficiency, security, and streamlined access. Together, these features underpin the PHD CI. The proposed CI incorporates a cloud risk mitigation strategy to address potential challenges such as cost fluctuations, service changes, and vendor lock-in, ensuring long-term sustainability, data portability, and operational resilience (see CCR).

Collaborations among stakeholders

In addition to the leadership role of CSDC, DG, JJC, JL, and JM in QUAREP^{6,77,118}, Imaging-PHD senior personnel (see Team Composition in MCP), are internationally recognized leading members of global community initiatives that have provided LoCs (see Sect. A&H, EFOR) and together represent hundreds of core facilities and thousands of individual researchers and their needs. For over 30 years, these communities have brought together researchers, CI professionals, and hardware vendors, specifically for the purpose of fostering collaboration and decision making. Interactions with the vendors have led to detailed discussions about the configurations of microscope hardware components^{119,120} and their capture in the inherently multi-modal NBO-Q^{2,6}. This work has laid the foundation for the proposed NGM specifications using open, common internet data formats (Obj.1). These discussions are currently centered on bioimaging, but the close interaction with vendors across communities incentivizes adoption of PHD in other disciplines (e.g., material sciences). Furthermore, the reliance of the Imaging-PHD CI on both the well-known PIDINST⁵⁰ and CoreMarketplace/RRID frameworks, the advisory role of AB and NH, and the workshop participation of CSDC in the NSF Research Coordination Network (RCN) entitled, “FAIR Instruments and core facilities”¹²⁹ mitigate the risk of overlooking the needs of stakeholders across a diverse array of domains (i.e., earth sciences, physics, astronomy, etc. See Mayernik, Mundoma, Johnson and Julian LOCs). The leadership team has met for over a year to share use-cases (Textbox 2) which have emerged from the individual organizations. This extensive preparation now ideally positions the Imaging-PHD team to ensure that this project is successful and addresses the needs of stakeholders across the research community, as demonstrated by diverse LOCs from research scientists, core facilities, instrument manufacturers, data management experts, IT and library departments, standards organizations and community organizations (see Sect. H, EFOR).

Measurable Outcomes

Objective 1: Definition of Next-Generation Metadata (NGM)

The NGM framework (Fig.4) and reference implementations will **enable manufacturers and research projects to create and extend specifications** representing their key outputs. In close connection with the NGFF community, led by team member JM and J. Swedlow, this work permits the automatic capture and storage of Hardware Descriptors along with associated instrument instances and acquired data. The development of dedicated hardware specifications like NBO-Q^{2,6} have demonstrated the need to extend the base specifications within the community, while the Bio-Formats¹¹² translation tool has shown that there is

no reliable way to provide backwards-compatibility between formats today. NGM will establish a standardized mechanism to capture third-party (community and/or industry) metadata in its entirety.

1-1- Deliverables (Obj.1)

The PHD consortium is committing itself to the development of NGM as a cornerstone of re-usable metadata through the following deliverables:

Deliverable 1-1: Core Linked Data Framework - Objective:

Specification of Core Linked Data Framework, crucial for defining hardware configurations across various domains. This work will leverage the W3C Resource Description Framework (RDF) and its JSON-LD serialization to facilitate creation and querying of interlinked graphs of metadata using standard, documented formats. Employing LinkML as the schema language, this framework aims to simplify schema definitions and integrate with ontologies. **Collaboration:** The OME team in Dundee will be instrumental in delivering an RDF-serialization version of the OME Data Model. Additionally, collaborators Hartley (BioImage Archive/REMBI) and Weidtkamp-Peters (NFDI4BIOIMAGE) will update their codebases to utilize this new framework to demonstrate its compatibility and practical utility with existing schema definitions. **Measurable Outcome:** Successful conversion and publication of the OME Data Model to LinkML will serve as a primary validation of the framework. The goal, however, is to drive the conversion of a maximal number of community schemas.

Deliverable 1-2: Hardware Descriptor Schema - Objective: Specification of the Hardware Descriptor Schema. This work builds on the published NBO-Q MM specification^{2,6} and on the microscope manufacturer outreach effort carried out by CSDC and DG in QUAREP to produce a consensus revision of the NBO-Q metadata schema^{119,120}. The NBO-Q XML schema, an adaptation of the OME XML schema, will be translated into the linked-data framework for detailed descriptions of microscopy hardware. **Collaboration:** A close collaboration with the RRID and PIDINST teams will ensure the maximum interoperability of NGM documents. Existing base specifications like DataCite will be used where possible. This will demonstrate the ability of working with new and *de novo* schemas. This deliverable will form the basis of a major upgrade of the MMA (Obj.2) to ingest NGM. These two components will be iteratively updated together with an initial stabilization version planned for the end of year 1. Feedback from other collaborators and surveys of community members, facilitated by the core feedback team - see Obj.4, will be iteratively incorporated into subsequent versions of the schema.

Measurable Outcome: The migration of the NBO-Q XML schema into the linked-data framework and integration of this new schema within the MMA as well as adoption by OME, QUAREP, and GBI community members will serve as indicators of success.

Deliverable 1-3: Software Components - Objective: Development of a software stack for utilizing the metadata framework to drive adoption and capacitate the creation and inspection of Hardware Descriptors. This includes data migration tools (e.g., XML-to-JSON) and validators, reference implementations in multiple languages (e.g., Java, Python, and JavaScript), and exemplary queries (e.g., in SPARQL). **Measurable Outcome:** The integration of these tools with existing codebases like OME and newly built packages as in Obj.2 and 3 will gauge the maturation and interoperability of the framework. The software repositories should attract external collaborators to guarantee the long-term sustainability of the projects.

Deliverable 1-4: Storage Backends - Objective: Guidelines and proofs-of-concept for the storage of Hardware Descriptors within alternative backends. Though the standalone PHD-ID-referenced document is a critical use of the metadata framework, Hardware Descriptors must also be transportable within other storage paradigms. We will prototype, test, and publish the use of OME-TIFF and OME-Zarr⁷⁹ as vessels for storing Hardware Descriptors. Additional storage backends might include the server-based RDMS

OMERO⁷⁶ or the light-weight research packaging format RO-Crate¹³⁰. **Collaboration:** Working directly with instrument manufacturers will facilitate **automated capture of Hardware Descriptor metadata** and eliminate the manual entry burden on biological researchers. **Measurable Outcome:** The developed guidelines for instrument export of metadata and the successful integration of the prototype using OME-TIFF and OME-Zarr formats for storing Hardware Descriptors will be assessed by the uptake and functionality of these formats in collaboration with microscope manufacturers and the QUAREP community. The number of sample data containing Hardware Descriptors will be checked in public archives like the BioImage Archive.

Deliverable 1-5: Community/Vendor Coordination - Objective: Facilitate communication between community and other stakeholders, identify requirements, coordinate the schema process. **Collaboration:** As a bridge between technologies and domains, NGM must respond to requirements from diverse communities. The establishment of a WG, perhaps situated within the RDA, will be undertaken. This WG may, for example, maintain a **registry of schemas** that are developed by the community to encourage re-use. Vendors who have specified their own machine-actionable schemas will need a process to relay concerns and agree on terminology. This work may be combined with a proposed ISO WG on MM, spearheaded by QUAREP, BINA, GBI and GerBI. **Measurable Outcome:** Success will be measured by the establishment and subsequent use of a process for open communication. The participation of vendors (e.g., meeting attendance), the integration of their feedback into community standards, and potential collaboration with the ISO WG on MM will be key indicators.

1-2- Sustained and sustainable impacts (Obj.1):

The NGM framework’s goal is to provide a flexible, extensible foundation for communities of FAIR practitioners to describe their outputs. The successful dissemination of the framework will: (1) **Reduce fragmentation:** Metadata schemas are currently silos requiring complex and time-consuming translation between themselves, whereas they should be able to coexist in harmony. (2) **Lower cost:** With less duplication of effort (e.g., translating schemas) and more re-use, the cost to develop and maintain data management solutions will be reduced. (3) **Drive standards compliance:** At the same time, by building on established W3C standards and closely working with the community to establish new standards, a new generation of tools can be built that work from the same first principles. (4) **Encourage collaboration:** The existence of easy-to-use tools (Obj.2) and reusable cyberinfrastructure (Obj.3) will provide an incentive for schema authors including vendors to build on foundational schemas to reduce their own development costs. (5) **Establish a web of data:** Ultimately, this unity in the representation of scientific outputs will lead to an interlinked graph of metadata which can be queried to discover new scientific insights. The number of independent schemas based on the NGM framework is a vital metric for Obj.1. For further metrics, please see “Delivery Mechanisms and Community Usage Metrics” (DMCUM).

Objective 2: Development of Micro-Meta Platform Frontend (MMPF)

A user-friendly MMPF GUI, building upon and expanding the functionality of the existing MMA^{81,82} and MME⁸², will enable the streamlined authoring, publication and exploration of NGM-specified Hardware Descriptor files for individual microscope instances (Figs. 2, 5-7). The use of standard API protocols (REST) will ensure the extensibility, usability and seamless integration of MMPF with the underlying MMPB (Obj.3) making it an effective tool for researchers and facility staff to manage

Fig. 5: Micro-Meta Platform Architecture: The tiers of the Micro-Meta Platform Backend (MMPB; Obj. 3; blue) are entirely hosted in the UMass Chan cloud. They serve as the hosting structure for the outputs of Obj. 1 (NGM-encoded Hardware Descriptor files, green) and Obj. 2 (MMP Frontend, red), which are presented as documents and web applications, respectively.

microscopy hardware information and data. **Collaborators:** To ensure comprehensive and accurate Hardware Descriptor integration, Obj.2 deliverables will rely on the unfunded collaboration with microscope hardware manufacturers (Leica, Nikon, Pico-QUANT, PCO, and Zeiss), core facilities, institutional libraries, and image RDMS and community initiatives (see Sect. H, EFOR).

2-1- Deliverables (Obj.2):

Deliverable 2-1: Extend Base Client Capabilities - **Objective:** To update the existing MMA and MME applications to better serve the project for all frontend interactions. Currently, MMA⁸¹ captures the characteristics of all hardware components of a microscope in a single NBO-Q^{2,6}-compliant file. This is achieved via an interactive graphical editor with which the user assembles icons corresponding to individual components and manually enters metadata (e.g., EFOR, Fig.2). Editing the entire Hardware Descriptor from scratch is tedious and error prone. A new version of the application will support authoring and importing pre-populated descriptions of individual hardware components, thus increasing accuracy and reducing time consuming tasks. This in turn will allow the evaluation of LLM-supported metadata entry. Based on the results of this exploratory work, additional improvements of the GUI will include the capacity to validate **LLM-suggested metadata** (see Obj.3), reducing manual effort while ensuring accuracy through strict human-in-the-loop guardrails. Tasks include: improving the React components **extensibility to other imaging modalities and scientific domains**; adding the capability to import descriptions of **individual hardware components** (e.g., Lasers, Filters, Cameras). **Measurable Outcome:** The success of this Deliverable will be measured by evaluating the diversity of hardware components recognized by the app and the increased accuracy and reduced time required for metadata entry through LLM-assisted workflows. Finally end-user satisfaction will be evaluated using surveys in collaboration with the Obj.4 team. Through unfund. collab. with hardware vendors (see Sect. H, EFOR) and further outreach, it is intended that a catalog of hardware components can be made available to further lower the burden on researchers.

Deliverable 2-2: Reading and Writing NGM Format - **Objective:** To enhance the MMA to be capable of automatically authenticating and ingesting NGM-formatted (Obj.1-2, Fig.4) Hardware Descriptors provided via unfunded collaboration with six major hardware vendors (see Sect. H, EFOR). **Measurable Outcome:** The seamless integration of manufacturer-provided metadata and simplification of metadata management for users will be ensured by the following enhanced features: (1) interpreting NGM schema, removing the current need to develop, maintain and support middleware translators capable of reading metadata out of multiple different manufacturer formats; (2) creating NGM output files, significantly improving the FAIR value of the Hardware Descriptor output produced by the proposed CI; (3) validating NGM objects through the integration of existing validation routines

Deliverable 2-3: Integration with the MMPB - **Objective:** To leverage the MMPB Service Tier (Fig.5) (see Obj.3-1) for automating time-consuming user tasks. **Integration tasks:** With the robust and scalable MMPB API facilitating more efficient data handling and storage, MMPF will be updated to include (Figs. 6&7): (1) Login with remote services (i.e., CoreMarketplace, and DataCite) to register instrument Basic Metadata and mint model-level RRDs, instrument-level PIDINST and PHD-IDs (Figs. 5&6). (2) Query CoreMarketplace to select existing core facilities. (3) Interact with MMPB (Figs. 5&7) to find microscopes with specific characteristics and identify, visualize and reuse Hardware Descriptors as templates to facilitate the description of new instruments (Fig.7). **Measurable Outcome:** The success of this Deliverable will be evaluated on the number of successful API transactions and user feedback on the system's reliability.

2-2 Sustained and sustainable impacts (Obj.2):

The following strategies will increase impact: (1) **Community:** The flexibility and interoperability afforded by NGM and expanded domain support is expected to foster the growth of versatile PHD platforms across different modalities and disciplines. (2) **Users:** The use of React will allow the integration of all enhancements into the easy-to-download MMA^{80,131} further lowering access barriers. (3) **Developers:** A modular strategy will facilitate the reuse of individual features as building blocks in third party platforms (e.g., integration of MMA in the 4DN and HuBMAP Data Portal and OMERO)^{123,126,132}. (4) **Manufacturers:** the availability of MMPF will promote the participation of instrument manufacturers in ensuring the production of rigorous, reproducible and FAIR image data.

Objective 3: Development of Micro-Meta Platform Backend (MMPB)

The MMPB provides a scalable infrastructure for the services of the PHD Platform. These include a **pre-publication collaborative space** for the authoring of Hardware Descriptor documents as well as a **searchable archive of published DOIs** implementing PIDINST and PHD-ID (Fig.2). PHDs are discovered through an internet crawling service or can be securely registered with the MMPB through participating institutions. Hosted by the UMass Chan Research Informatics Core and capable of **minting DOIs** via the Resource Description and Access license of the

UMass Library System, MMPB promises a robust and citable repository for community-sanctioned microscope Hardware Descriptors. The MMPB can additionally be installed, hosted, and adapted to meet multi-modality and -disciplinary use cases elsewhere, expanding the reach of PHDs.

3-1- Deliverables (Obj.3):

Deliverable 3-1 MMPB Development and Deployment - Objective: Providing a comprehensive service backend for the PHD project within the first year. **Proposed Infrastructure:** UMass Chan's cloud-based infrastructure is the backbone of this development, offering a suite of tools and informatics technology services. This infrastructure adheres to top-tier data standards, providing a safe, secure and efficient environment for the MMPB. The leadership support from UMass Chan endorses the project's vision (see LOC from Barnett, Coleman, Langlois, Piorun and Wolf), ensuring successful deployment, scalability, and adaptability. The envisioned five-tiered solution (Fig.5) includes: (1) **Micro-Meta Database Tier:** Serving both as a pre-publication database of Hardware Descriptors generated using the MMPF, and a search index of discovered Hardware Descriptors. (2) **The UMass Chan Foundry Tier:** Engineered as a comprehensive data repository that efficiently catalogs and indexes data, including the UMass-published DOI repository, the Foundry facilitates easy access and retrieval for users. (3) **The Micro-Meta Platform PID-Services Tier:** Retrieves RRIDs for instrument model and core facility; streamlines the process to request DOIs through the UMass Library DataCite license to implement PIDINST and PHD-ID; integrates with the CoreMarketplace/RRIDs system; facilitates communication with UMass Foundry Backend; and provides read-only and enhanced access interfaces to different user groups. (4) **Micro-Meta Platform Web Application Hosting Tier:** Centralizes hosting and ensures seamless access and reliable performance. The smart React MME component will enable users to identify microscopes that align with their scientific needs, while the UMass Chan Foundry client will unify access to all repository functions. (5) **LLM Integration Tier:** As an exploratory effort, we will integrate LLMs to extract structured metadata aligned with NBO-Q standards from technical instrument documentation (e.g., spec-sheets, brochures, part-lists, patents, publications). This approach will leverage prompt engineering techniques to efficiently interpret and extract relevant metadata. These LLM workflows aim to enhance the accuracy and speed of metadata generation. A collection of curated microscope technical documentation (see Obj.4) will be stored in a cloud-based AWS S3 bucket, ensuring secure, scalable, and accessible storage for future Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)¹³³ based LLM optimization efforts.

Scalability and System Robustness: MMPB is engineered for scalability, ensuring it can adapt to varying demands and data influxes. The infrastructure is subject to regular evaluations and adheres to stringent security protocols, including advanced encryption and continuous external audits. The system is fortified with Multi-Factor Authentication and is equipped to handle shifts in the digital landscape, thanks to its

Fig. 6: The Imaging-PHD process for the persistent identification of Microscope instances and publication of Hardware Descriptors, consists of three easy steps: 1) The stand-alone Micro-Meta App or the Micro-Meta Platform-Frontend (Obj. 2) are used to capture, edit and manage NGM-encoded Hardware Descriptors files (Obj. 1). 2) Hardware Descriptors are loaded into Micro-Meta Platform (Obj. 3; Fig. 5) allowing users to request: i) an RRID for the Core Facility hosting the instrument (if relevant) and for the Instrument Model through CoreMarketplace; ii) a PIDINST for the Instrument Instance using the DataCite implementation through the UMass Lamar Soutter Library; iii) a PHD-ID for the Hardware through DataCite. 3) The Hardware Descriptor containing associated PIDs (i.e., RRID(s), PIDINST and PHD-ID) are published for persistent storage to be used as described in Fig. 7.

integrative APIs. Additionally, data redundancy and a comprehensive disaster recovery plan safeguard against potential system disruptions. **Measurable Outcome:** The primary measure of success will be the smooth launch of the MMPB system, gauged by the system's operational stability, the absence of critical bugs or system crashes, and the effective integration of the React MME component.

Deliverable 3-2 Micro-Meta Platform

Maintenance/Support - **Objective:** Providing continuous updates, bug fixes, and user support for the MMPB. A **maintenance plan** will establish a routine schedule for system updates and improvements, focusing on enhancing system performance and adding new features based on user feedback. The provided **support structure** will consist of a dedicated helpdesk and user support system, including FAQs, user guides, and a ticketing system for handling queries and issues. **Measurable**

Outcome: Delivery will focus on the effectiveness and frequency of system updates and bug fixes, aiming to reduce post-update issues and achieve a bug resolution time of under 2 working days. Success will also be measured by the consistent functionality and reliability of the MMPB as well as user engagement, indicated by registration rates, system usage frequency, and positive user feedback.

Deliverable 3-3 Synchronization of RRIDs with CoreMarketplace Instrumentation Database

Objective: Develop full data exchange with MMPB through open, public, documented REST APIs between CoreMarketplace and RRIDs codifying and automating RRID assignment by core facilities while maintaining human-in-the-loop curation ensuring consistency of metadata (Fig.5). **Integration tasks:** Improve interactions between MMPB, the existing CoreMarketplace instrument model database¹²⁸, and the RRID registry, using REST API calls and standardized data formats ensuring the list of instrument models is comprehensive, unified, and includes PIDINST and detailed PHDs. A core facility user in the CoreMarketplace, a MMPF user or an author required to add RRIDs to their manuscript will have the ability to interact with the most up-to-date shared information from any system. This addition will not only register the instrument but also capture its corresponding PIDINST and PHD, making the data available in all systems as soon as it is approved. Furthermore, the curation team will “seed” this work with data from unfund. collab. vendors (Sect. H, EFOR). **Measurable Outcome:** A comprehensive list of “off-the-shelf” microscope models, their Hardware Descriptors and appropriate PIDs will be made available to all RRID-, PIDINST- and PHD-aware systems.

Deliverable 3-4 Automate the Seamless Generation of PIDs

Objective: Establish connections between MMPB and external platforms to simplify usage of MMPF (Fig.6). **Development goals:** (1) create links to CoreMarketplace and model RRIDs; (2) leverage the UMass Chan DataCite license to obtain PIDINSTs for instrument instances and PHD-IDs for Hardware Descriptors; (3) publish citable Hardware Descriptors with all relevant PIDs. **Integration Tasks:** Developing open, standardized APIs and data exchange protocols to link the MMPB with CoreMarketplace, RRIDs and DataCite documenting all inter-system API calls for possible, future collaborations will enable persistent identification of microscope instances and metadata capture in the PIDINST schema. **Measurable Outcome:** Metrics include the number of PIDs generated, with a focus on how effectively they are created and utilized within our ecosystem. Qualitative metrics (i.e., user-surveys) will be used to assess users’ satisfaction.

Deliverable 3-5 PHD-aware Search Indexing Enhancements

Objective: Enhancing the UMass Chan Foundry’s Elastic framework for indexing to include capabilities for NGM-detection, improved data retrieval and management, and exploration via MMPF. **Development Goals:** Implementing the

Elasticsearch framework⁸³ to facilitate efficient indexing and quick retrieval of data within the MMPB. Discovered documents will be stored in the Tier 1 database (Fig.5). Modifications to the framework itself will be contributed upstream to benefit other sites. **Measurable Outcome:** The speed and accuracy of data retrieval within the system, aiming for significant improvements in search response times and data relevancy.

3-2- Sustained and sustainable impacts

MMPB development is designed to significantly influence the field of scientific data management. Its primary goal is to establish a robust CI for efficiently storing and accessing Hardware Descriptors. This endeavor is crucial for supporting ongoing scientific research and enhancing collaborative efforts. Key aspects contributing to the project's sustainable impact include: (1) **Robust and Scalable Infrastructure:** Hosted on UMass Chan's advanced cloud infrastructure, the MMPB is built to be interoperable, scalable and adaptable, ready to meet evolving data requirements while maintaining high standards of reliability and security. (2) **Maintenance and Support Framework:** With a focus on providing ongoing updates, bug fixes, and user support, the project is dedicated to maintaining a system that remains functional, reliable, and responsive to user needs. (3) **Facilitating Rigorous Scientific Research:** By enabling precise documentation of hardware configurations used in data generation, the project directly contributes to the rigor and reproducibility of scientific experiments, enhancing the validity and reliability of research outcomes. (4) **Extensibility Across Research Domains:** While initially centered around microscopy in biological imaging, the project's infrastructure is designed to be interoperable with other scientific fields, widening its scope and impact. Overall, the MMPB development aims to significantly impact scientific data management by creating a robust, maintainable, and adaptable system that enhances efficiency, collaboration, and transparency in scientific research.

Objective 4: Coordinated Consulting, Testing, Validation, Outreach and Dissemination (CTVOD)

User-feedback and outreach plays a pivotal role throughout the lifetime of this project. Obj.4 therefore sets out mechanisms to: (1) provide critical input early in the design process; (2) carry out beta-testing at the level of technical lab-based expertise, facility usage, small business application and community organizations; (3) develop and present outreach and teaching materials; and (4) create a curated corpus of microscopy-related technical documentation to be used for future LLM efforts.

4-1- Deliverables (Obj.4):

Deliverable 4-1: Consulting Ahead of Development - **Objective:** Diverse input is crucial for creating widely usable products for the wider community. Building on early adopters^{123,126,134,135} evaluations of MMA⁸⁰, the Obj.4 team (JL, DG & JJC teams) will gather feedback to ensure the Leadership team (see MCP) keeps abreast of users' needs. In addition to leveraging the funded collaboration from librarians and imaging core facility staff, the team will leverage their leadership positions in community efforts and the extensive network of supporting community leaders (EFOR, Sections A&H) to facilitate focus groups. Impromptu discussions and regular meetings will provide frequent input in the early phase of the project. JJC's facility offers real-world testing scenarios, while JL's experience in microscopy-based open science projects adds a unique perspective to the team. **Measurable outcome:** Three half-day planning sessions within the first six months of funding will produce a prioritized development plan combining Obj.4 team and key stakeholders' inputs (focus groups, surveys) to be continually fine-tuned by month 12.

Deliverable 4-2: Improved Usability by Integrated User-evaluation - **Objective:** Directly involve research scientists, funded core facility personnel, and data librarians during all phases of development via a tiered and structured feedback process to tabulate feedback from testers. In the second half of year 1, the Obj.4 team will transition from consulting to testing and providing feedback. This transition will end at year 2 while testing/feedback will continue through the end of the grant. Testing will be conducted in a step-wise manner: (1) UMass Chan team members that have immediate access to the development team starting with MH from the DG lab, due to his extensive experience with the stand alone MMA; (2) JL and the JJC team, each providing detailed and candid feedback; (3) library staff and funded imaging core facility staff will be asked to provide feedback via user surveys questions such as "ease of use", "data entry speed", "suggestions for improvements" etc. The team will meet biweekly via video conference to discuss feedback emerging from repeated development/testing cycles, address possible miscommunications and resolve issues prior to

release. As needed, the team will employ the same mechanisms for community feedback solicitation described in 4-1. **Measurable outcome:** Qualitative metrics based on user surveys, in combination with continual consultations (~20/yr) and validation by the Obj.4 team as an essential service to the development team.

Deliverable 4-3: Training and Education (T&E) Strategy - Objective: Educate research scientists on the importance of FAIR RDMS, PIDs, and MM documentation. Starting from year 3, the main tasks of the Obj.4 team will be the creation of **outreach strategies and materials** for the Imaging-PHD CI. JJC has trained >4000 individuals and found that new tasks are better learned one-on-one or by short video walkthroughs. Hence, virtual drop-in office hours will be advertised, scheduled and posted online (in anonymized fashion) via the teams' extensive networks and community organizations (see EFOR, Sections A&H), in addition to presentations and workshops organized at conferences. DG and MH have extensive experience in the creation of independent learning modules (ILMs) for light microscopy and will support JJC in creating asynchronous online teaching modalities and FAQs. Mr. Horrman and other undergraduate students working primarily in DG lab will ensure that the produced training material is tailored to student needs. In addition, opportunities will be sought for existing COOP-students in the DG lab to contribute to the project as appropriate. **Measurable outcome:** Outreach strategies, ILMs, training videos, workshop/conference/community presentations. Qualitative metrics based on user surveys will be used to evaluate reaching T&E goals.

Deliverable 4-4: Curated corpus of microscope technical material - Objective: As adoption of the CI will increase during year 4, end-users authoring Hardware Descriptors files will be encouraged to contribute to community-wide Machine Learning efforts by depositing related technical microscopy documentation into the MMPB database (see Obj.3). This material will be curated by the Obj.4 team to ensure accuracy and usability for future LLM training efforts. **Measurable outcome:** A growing corpus of curated microscopy technical material for future LLM efforts.

4-2- Sustained and sustainable impacts (Obj.4):

Consulting, Testing and Validation of systems directly contribute to the sustainability of the other objectives. Additional sustainable impacts, resulting from outreach and dissemination are: (1) **Increased awareness:** the extensive education and training effort conducted in Obj.4 will increase awareness of the importance of FAIR data, PIDs and Metadata Standards for increasing the rigor, reproducibility, and reuse of image data and for improving the societal impact, efficiency, equitability and sustainability of the research enterprise. (2) **Training materials and Documentation:** asynchronous T&E material (videos, slide decks, ILMs, extended documentation) will be sustained by advertising throughout the community and deposition to the BINA MicroscopyDB¹³⁶, eScholarship@UMassChan¹³⁷, Zenodo, and community YouTube channels. In addition to graduate microscopy course material, simplified starter-packs for K12 teachers, high-school and undergraduate students will be developed, tested and distributed via existing school outreach programs at UMass Chan, like ScienceLIVE¹³⁸. (3) **Community development:** early NIH 4DN consortium standardization efforts have been sustained by fueling activities like BINA and QUAREP and providing the basis for community standards development^{2,5,80}. Similarly much of the sustained impact of the products of Obj.4 will manifest through community propagation. (4) **LLM training resources:** The authoritative corpus of microscopy-related hardware technical descriptions will be used as an outside knowledge base for RAG-supported¹³³ response generation in the future, creating a robust foundation for domain-specific applications and augmented search capabilities.

Metrics for all Objectives: Please reference the DMCUM supplemental document.

Long-term Sustainability for all Objectives:

Different strategies are required to ensure the sustainable impact of the different PHD CI deliverables: (1) NGM will be adopted by OME and QUAREP, including its large industry membership. (2) MMPF is a centerpiece of CSDC's work to expand NBO-Q² in partnership with QUAREP^{6,9,119,120} and community and industry unfund. collab. (Sect. H, EFOR). As such its functionalities will remain available as part of the stand-alone Micro-Meta App^{80,131} and through integration in third-party data portals (e.g., OMERO, 4DN, HubMAP)^{123,126,132}. (3) MMPB responds to the needs of diverse stakeholders in the community (Textbox 2; Sect. H, EFOR) to pool resources to build a nationwide FAIR infrastructure for imaging data as

demonstrated by several opinion papers and responses to pertinent NIH Requests for Information (RFIs)¹³⁹⁻¹⁴¹. As such, Imaging-PHD will continue to be supported through UMass Chan Library and IT resources (see Sect. H, EFOR) and through its integration with CoreMarketplace and RRID as demand for interoperable, extensible, flexible, and openly accessible solutions will only increase in the future. In addition, its reusable tiered architecture will facilitate sustainability through adoption by institutions (i.e., academic libraries and manufacturers) and community initiatives (e.g., OME open-source sustainability strategy).

The SciCrunch Antibody Registry (led by AB)²⁴, iRODS¹⁴² & the NIST Genome Editing Consortium¹⁴³ are successful examples of transitioning from federal funding to self-sufficiency and balancing open access with the need to generate revenue through a cost-sharing partnership with industry.

This blueprint will be leveraged to develop an exploratory business model for the long-term financial sustainability of the PHD CI. Specifically, the strong relationship all members of the Imaging-PHD team have with institutions, community initiatives, and vendors will be exploited to explore the revenue potential of our scalable CI while upholding open access: (1) **Manufacturer Partnerships for Revenue and Support:** As cornerstone of our financial strategy we will investigate establishing partnerships in which manufacturers will contribute financially or in-kind to the CI in exchange for access. This would not only generate consistent revenue but also foster collaborative technical advancements. (2) **Diversified Revenue Streams:** While protecting open access for academic institutions and researchers, we will explore alternative revenue streams, including specialized services, consulting, and technical support to industry partners, as well as potential licensing opportunities for technology developed within the Imaging-PHD system. (3) **Efficient Modular Design for Reduced Operational Costs:** In general, the modular design of our CI allows for economical maintenance and upgrading, significantly lowering operational expenses and ensuring the efficient use of financial resources.

D.6 Broader impacts

Beyond addressing urgent community needs, the PHD CI impacts Sustained Scientific Innovation by enabling the generation and sharing of reproducible, well-documented datasets that are persistently linked from the full provenance chain. Additional impact dimensions are: (1) **Advancing Research Integrity and Scientific Discovery:** Standardized, persistent and citable Hardware Descriptors containing comprehensive metadata contribute to research integrity by minimizing errors in data acquisition and analysis thus providing a solid foundation for expediting scientific progress. (2) **Facilitating Interdisciplinary Research:** The adoption of FAIR data principles and the development of NGM provides a common language and framework for sharing data across different imaging modalities, data types and scientific domains. (3) **Democratizing Access to Technology:** The CI open-access platform for authoring and publishing Hardware Descriptors, along with powerful search capabilities, is crucial to democratize recognition for scientific development and access to needed technologies for researchers in resource-constrained environments. To further increase the PHD CI's equitability impact, a collaboration was initiated with the Africa PID Alliance⁹⁰ effort to develop PIDs for the global south produced research resources and output (see Owango LOC; Sect. H, EFOR) (4) **Empowering core facility Staff:** Recognizing the vital role played by core facility staff in research, the project elevates their contributions by facilitating tracking their work in reports, grants and publications. (5) **Enhancing Data Management and Sharing:** The project aligns with the evolving expectations of funding agencies and publishers for well-documented, reusable datasets that benefit the broader scientific community. (6) **Educational and Training Opportunities:** The coordinated outreach and training strategy of the project equips students and researchers with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively utilize the PHD CI, thus contributing to workforce development in an increasingly sought-after field. This educational component has a multiplier effect as trained researchers foster a culture of data stewardship and quality in their respective institutions. (7) **Efficiency Benefits:** Existing cost-benefit analyses^{14,16,91} underscore the multiplicative economic advantages of adopting PIDs and standardized metadata practices. (8) **Global Collaboration:** Through collaboration with international community initiatives, the project fosters a global network of stakeholders dedicated to advancing microscopy and RDMS.

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